

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF THIODICYANDIAMIDINE WITH METALLIC ELEMENTS. PART I

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Thiodicyandiamidine (guanylthiourea) has been found to act as a bifunctional ligand yielding complexes of the inner metallic type with copper and nickel. The constitution of these complexes has been discussed.

Thiodicyandiamidine or guanylthiourea (I) has been found to act as a bifunctional ligand resembling biguanide and dicyandiamidine, yielding, with bivalent metals like copper and nickel, complex compounds of the inner metallic type (II).

It can react in either of its tautomeric forms (a) or (b) to give rise to inner metallic complexes of the structures shown below :

[Me = Cu or Ni]

As the colour of the copper complex is brown, while that of nickel is orange, it may be assumed that the configuration of the former corresponds to the structure (II b) and that of the latter to (II a). For, it is well known that all nickel complexes of the inner metallic type, with the nickel atom linked to four N atoms in the complex, are yellow, orange or red. Typical instances of this are furnished by the ligands like biguanides and glyoximes. The brown colour of copper complex suggests strongly of the presence of a copper—sulphur bond. This is further supported by its ready decomposition into black sulphide of copper. The corresponding nickel complex, on the other hand, fails to give any nickel sulphide even with boiling alkali solutions. Then again, while nickel combines, as usual, with two molecules of thiodicyandiamidine filling up all the four co-ordination positions, copper unites with only one molecule of the ligand occupying two of its co-ordination positions, the other two being filled up by water molecules (III). This constitutes an important distinction between copper and nickel in respect of their thiodicyandiamidine complexes. But the configuration

(IV) for the nickel complex with two free amino groups would rather make it behave as a diacidic base like its biguanide analogues. But the fact that the compound is incapable of forming salts with acids may be attributed to the presence of the acidic

thio-amido group $S=C_1-NH_2$ in the molecule. This is also in parallel with the behaviour of nickel dicyandiamidine complex. So, while the nickel ion reacts with thiodicyandiamidine in its tautomeric form (I a), copper reacts more easily with its thiol form (I b).

Measurement of magnetic susceptibilities indicates that the copper and nickel complexes possess planar configuration with ds^2 hybrid bonds.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Thiodicyandiamidine was prepared from dicyandiamide and sulphuretted hydrogen according to the method described by Bamberger (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 1460). Oxalate of the base was prepared from the product of the reaction with ammonium oxalate and oxalic acid, and purified by recrystallisation. (Found : N, 31.63 ; S, 17.90 ; oxalic acid, 34.06. $2C_2H_5N_4S.C_2H_2O_4.4H_2O$ requires N, 31.0 ; S, 17.60 ; oxalic acid, 34.80 per cent).

From the oxalate, pure base was obtained by treatment with baryta solution ; m. p. of the base, 160° . (Found : N, 47.10 ; S, 26.90. $C_2H_5N_4S$ requires N, 47.45 ; S, 27.10 per cent).

Cupric monothiodicyandiamidine sulphate was obtained as a brown precipitate when a solution of copper sulphate (1.25 g.) was added to that of thiodicyandiamidine (1.18 g.). The product was filtered, washed with cold water, and then dried in air. The substance is insoluble in cold water, but slightly soluble in hot water ; the solution yields a white precipitate of $BaSO_4$ with barium chloride. On warming with dilute acid or alkali solution it gives a black precipitate of copper sulphide. On heating to 105° it blackens due to the formation of copper sulphide. {Found : Cu, 21.06 ; N, 18.43 ; S (total), 15.82 ; SO_4 , 15.78 ; H_2O (by loss at 100°), 11.66. $[Cu(C_2H_5N_4S)(H_2O)_2]_2.SO_4.4H_2O$ requires Cu, 21.13 ; N, 18.63 ; S (total), 15.97 ; SO_4 , 15.96 ; H_2O (4 mol.), 11.96 per cent}.

The substance (dried at 100°) gives Cu, 23.90; S(total), 18.20; $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{SO}_4$ requires Cu, 24.01; S(total), 18.14 per cent.

Cupric monothiodicyandiamidine hydroxide was obtained from a cold solution of copper sulphate (1.25 g.) and that of thiodicyandiamidine (1.18 g.) in the presence of an excess of ammonium hydroxide. The product was filtered, washed with cold water, and then dried in a desiccator to a constant weight.

The substance forms brown crystals, insoluble in water and alcohol. It liberates ammonia from solutions of ammonium salts. It is decomposed by warm dilute hydrochloric acid with separation of black sulphide of copper. When heated to 100° it blackens due to the formation of CuS. {Found: Cu, 27.38; N, 24.12; S, 13.64. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{OH}$ requires Cu, 27.19; N, 23.98; S, 13.70 per cent}.

Nickel tris-thiodicyandiamidine was prepared by the addition of a solution of nickel sulphate (1.4 g.) to that of thiodicyandiamidine (1.18 g.) in the presence of a large excess of caustic soda. The orange coloured precipitate was filtered, washed with cold water and dried in a desiccator to a constant weight. The substance is insoluble in water and alcohol. It liberates ammonia from ammonium salts, but is unaffected by boiling caustic soda solution. It is readily decomposed by warm dilute acids. {Found: Ni, 18.40; N, 34.91; S, 19.90; H_2O (by loss at 100°), 8.10. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})_3]$, 1.5 H_2O requires Ni, 18.35; N, 35.03; S, 20.01; H_2O , 8.40 per cent}.

{Found (for the anhydrous substance): Ni, 20.09; N, 38.06; S, 21.90. Calc. Ni, 20.05; N, 38.26; S, 21.86 per cent}.

Magnetic Susceptibilities.—The magnetic susceptibilities of the compounds were measured in a Gouy's balance. The results are given below.

Substance	Xg.	$\chi_M(\text{obs.})$	δ (diamagnetic correction.)	$\chi_M(\text{corr.})$	μ_B .
1. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.70×10^{-6}	1623×10^{-6}	207×10^{-6}	1830×10^{-6}	1.50
2. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{OH}$	3.45×10^{-6}	805.5×10^{-6}	65.6×10^{-6}	871×10^{-6}	1.46
3. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})_3] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Diamagnetic				

The moment values for the copper atom in the copper complexes are somewhat lower than the theoretical value of $1.73 \mu_B$, which suggests an unusually high temperature effect.